

Data Table 1. Raw counts of dissected and viable spores for each strain assayed in this study.					
Genotype	Strain	Viable spores / Dissected spores	Spore viability (%)	Standard Error	95% CI
Hybrid, wild type	N17 x W303 (YDG853)	5/1076	0.46%	0.21%	0.16% - 1.12%
Hybrid, pCLB2-MSH2	N17 x W303 (YDG964)	28/880	3.18%	0.59%	2.19% - 4.58%
Hybrid, pCLB2-SGS1	N17 x W303 (YDG912)	429/2136	20.08%	0.87%	18.44% - 21.84%
Hybrid, pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	N17 x W303 (YDG982)	2660/8148	32.65%	0.52%	31.64% - 33.67%
<i>S.paradoxus</i> , wild type	N17 (YDG965)	369/400	92.25%	1.34%	89.18% - 94.52%
<i>S.cerevisiae</i> , wild type	W303 (YDG979)	335/400	83.75%	1.84%	79.80% - 87.06%
<i>S.paradoxus</i> , pCLB2-SGS1	N17 (YDG965)	351/400	87.75%	1.64%	84.15% - 90.63%
<i>S.cerevisiae</i> , pCLB2-SGS1	W303 (YDG979)	323/396	81.56%	1.95%	77.44% - 85.09%
<i>S. par.</i> , pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	N17 (YDG980)	363/400	90.75%	1.45%	87.48% - 93.24%
<i>S. cer.</i> , pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	W303 (YDG981)	272/360	75.55%	2.27%	70.85% - 79.72%